

EFFICIENT OPERATION OF THE RAIN IRRIGATION UNIT

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Annotation: The article discusses the advantages and disadvantages of water-saving technologies, including sprinkler irrigation, and their application, taking into account local conditions.

Keywords: Agriculture, irrigation, springkler, frugality, technology, machanism, soil, salinity.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются преимущества и недостатки водосберегающих технологий, в том числе дождевания, и их применение с учетом местных условий.

Ключевые слова: Сельское хозяйство, орошение, шпринклер, бережливость, технология, техника, почва, засоление.

The demand for water resources is increasing year by year due to factors such as population growth, increased food demand, expansion of industrial production, and climate change in the countries of the world. As a result, in many regions of the world, there is a trend of water resource scarcity.

It is known that the agricultural sector is the largest user of water in the whole world. Therefore, the entire scientific community emphasizes the efficient use of water in agriculture, especially in irrigated agricultural fields, including the widespread introduction of water-saving technologies, as the most priority way to alleviate water shortages.

80% of the consumed water resources are formed on the territory of neighboring countries. Effective use of Uzbekistan's water resources, especially in order to alleviate the water shortage that has been increasing in recent years, is the wide introduction of water-saving systems of crop irrigation and expansion of the possibilities of using modern technologies in the management of water resources. it is permissible to admit that he is taking the initiative among the countries of the region.

In the last five years, a number of decrees and decisions on the development of the water sector, the introduction of water-saving technologies were adopted by the honorable President Sh. Mirziyoyev, and as a result of them, in order to encourage agricultural producers who introduced new irrigation technology, the state establishment of the mechanism for allocating subsidies, creation of a number of benefits for producers of agricultural goods made a fundamental turn in the development of irrigated agriculture. As a result of the attention of the state leadership, the improvement of the necessary legal norms and the consistent application in practice, the scope of introducing water-

saving irrigation systems in our country has increased dramatically in recent years. In 2021 alone, the areas where water-saving technologies have been introduced will increase by 5 times and cover 22% of the total irrigated areas, and in the next five to seven years, this indicator is set to reach 50%. The Parliament of our country is also conducting large-scale work on improving the legislation in the field of water management.

As the head of our state emphasized the need to approach every issue with science and experience, advanced modern technologies were brought from foreign countries, and their specialists were involved. Due to the year-by-year expansion of the areas where these technologies are introduced, many enterprises have been established in our country, and the production of irrigation system equipment has been started in local conditions.

Now, there is a need for local personnel who build modern water-saving irrigation systems and provide them with service services. At the same time, the issues of creative approach to these irrigation systems, their improvement, adaptation to the unique soil and climate conditions of Uzbekistan are becoming more relevant day by day, and this is required by life itself.

At the present time, when climate change has become a global problem, the efficient use of water resources has become the agenda. In addition, the demand for water in Uzbekistan is increasing due to the wasteful use of natural water, which may exhaust the limited resources of mankind, the continuous increase in the number of people and consumption according to the laws of population, and high economic growth rates.

The growing population of the world, including Uzbekistan, causes the demand for food products to increase year by year. In a situation where the available amounts of water resources, which are the main source of food production, are decreasing, the issue of developing effective methods of their use, economical use of existing water resources is becoming more urgent day by day.

In such conditions, the use of water-saving technologies of crop irrigation is being widely implemented in most countries of the world in order to use water sparingly without wasting water. In this regard, countries such as Israel, Japan, Jordan, China, USA, Italy, Turkey, Greece (Greece), Australia and India have achieved great results.

Located in the center of the Asian continent, thousands of kilometers away from the ocean and seas, our country is one of the only 2 countries in the world that requires crossing the borders of at least 2 other countries to access the world ocean, in a dry and hot region. is located. As mentioned above, in the conditions of the Republic of Uzbekistan, where the waters of the main rivers flow from the trans-border areas, the water resources are effective.

Due to the excessive use of water by the extensive agriculture of our country, the problem of shortage of water resources primarily affects the water supply of irrigated areas, and this effect is increasing year by year. In such conditions, the use of water-saving technologies of crop irrigation will further

increase the value of these blessings.

For this purpose, with the initiatives of the President, in the last five years, the state has paid great attention to the widespread introduction of water-saving technologies of crop irrigation. In particular, a number of benefits, such as exemption from taxes and allocation of subsidies by the state, were created for agricultural producers who introduced water-saving irrigation systems.

As a result, the areas where water-saving technologies are used in our republic are expanding year by year. In this process, of course, there is an increasing need for qualified national specialists who implement water-saving irrigation systems, use them, and provide service.

The need to train qualified local personnel for the field of water management, improve the system of improving their qualifications, develop mutual cooperation between education, science, and production sectors, and introduce the production of scientific achievements and know-how It is one of the most important strategic tasks of our country.

In particular, according to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-6024 of July 10, 2020 "On approval of the concept of water management development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the years 2020-2030", the areas where water-saving irrigation technologies are used in our country 2030 2 million per year. per hectare, according to the Decision PQ-5005 of February 24, 2021 "On approval of the strategy of water resources management and irrigation sector development in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2021-2023" the task of rapidly expanding its area and bringing it up to 800,000 hectares in 2023 has been set.

As a result of comprehensive support at the level of the state leadership, effective work has been carried out in recent years to raise the living standards of the country's population to higher levels by increasing the quantity and quality of the harvest obtained from irrigated areas based on the effective use of water resources.

In the course of our scientific research work, in the Karavulbazar district of the Bukhara region, we carried out several works on improving the efficiency of sprinkler irrigation machines, which are one of the water-saving technologies, as well as adapting them to the conditions of the area (Fig. 1).

The conducted studies have shown that several shortcomings have arisen during sprinkler irrigation. That is:

- high demand for metal for machines and devices;
- a lot of energy consumption in the irrigation process (40-100 KWh of electricity is used to implement $m=300$ m³/ha);
- low productivity at large irrigation rates;
- uneven distribution of water in strong wind, increased evaporation;
- complexity of irrigation technology;
- limited use in saline lands;
- Disruption of the structure of the surface layer of the soil, formation of crust.

1 – picture. The process of using sprinkler irrigation machines

But as a result of studies, we found out that there are several advantages along with the above disadvantages:

- it is possible to change the depth of soil salinization through the irrigation rate;
- increasing the relative humidity of the surface layer of the air and lowering its temperature, ensuring that crops are not hit by cold;
- equal distribution of water across the field and no demand for its terrain;
- there is no need to build irrigation ditches and ditches;
- the possibility of giving mineral fertilizers with irrigation water;
- the ability to adapt to irrigation;
- water saving method, high water use coefficient (WCF);
- high land use coefficient (LCF).

In conclusion, it should be noted that in the conditions of Uzbekistan, which is located in an arid region, agriculture is the sector that consumes the most water. About 90% of available water resources are used for agricultural production. In recent years, the state has made it possible to effectively use existing water resources based on the widespread introduction of water-saving irrigation technologies in the irrigation of agricultural crops. As a result, the available water reserves are saved.

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